

Kinetics and Mechanistic Approach of The Oxidation of Some Diols by Benzimidazolium Dichromate in Dimethylsulfoxide Medium

Paper Id : 20675 Submission Date : 2025-08-05 Acceptance Date : 2025-08-23 Publication Date : 2025-08-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17264627

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Chandra Prakash Saini

Assistant Professor
Department Of Chemistry
Seth R L Saharia
Govt.P.G.College
Kaladera,Rajasthan, India

Dinesh Panday

Assistant Professor
Department Of Chemistry
Mohanlal Sukhadia
University
Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

Abstract

Kinetics of oxidation of four vicinal, four non-vicinal diols, and one of their monoethers by benzimidazolium dichromate (BIDC) have been studied. The vicinal diols yield products arising out of the glycol bond fission while the other diols yield hydroxycarbonyl compounds. The reaction is first order with respect to BIDC. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics are observed with respect to the diols. The oxidation of [1,1,2,2-²H₄] ethane diol exhibited primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.78$ at 308K). the rate constants of oxidation of four vicinal diols show excellent correlation with Taft's $\sum\sigma^*$ values with negative reaction constant, ρ^* . A mechanism involving glycol-bond fission has been proposed for the oxidation of the vicinal diols. The other diols are oxidised by a hydride-transfer mechanism as they are monohydric alcohols.

Keywords

Diols, Benzimidazolium Dichromate, Kinetics, Oxidation, Correlation, Mechanism.

Introduction

Specific and selective oxidation of organic compounds under non-aqueous conditions is an important reaction in synthetic organic chemistry. For this a wide range of compounds containing Cr(VI) have been demonstrated to be efficient reagents in organic synthesis and have been used in both aqueous and non-aqueous conditions for the oxidation of organic compounds [1-4]. There is continued interest in the development of new Cr(VI) reagents for the effective and selective oxidation of organic substrates, in particular alcohols, under mild conditions. Therefore, the search for new oxidizing agents is of interest to synthetic organic chemists.

Benzimidazolium dichromate is also one such oxidant developed recently. It is a more efficient and stronger oxidizing agent. This new compound is more efficient for quantitative oxidation of several organic substrates and has certain advantages over similar oxidizing agents in terms of the amount of oxidant and solvent required, short reaction times and high yields.

Objective of study

1. **To determine the rate law** for the oxidation of different diols under varying experimental conditions such as substrate concentration, oxidant concentration, and solvent polarity.
2. **To evaluate the influence of substituents and molecular structure** of diols on their reactivity and oxidation behaviour.
3. **To study the effect of temperature** on the reaction rate and to calculate activation parameters such as activation energy (E_a), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger).
4. **To explore the mechanistic pathway** of oxidation by analysing kinetic data, reaction intermediates, and the role of the solvent medium.
5. **To compare the efficiency of benzimidazolium dichromate (BIDC)** as an oxidizing agent with other chromium(VI) oxidants in similar systems.
6. **To provide insights into the applicability of BIDC** in selective oxidation reactions, which may be relevant in organic synthesis and green chemistry perspectives.

Review of Literature

The kinetics of oxidation of organic diols has been studied by many reagents, such as butyltriphenylphosphonium Dichromate[5], isoquinolinium dichromate[6], tripropylammonium fluorochromate[7], 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate[8], bromine in acid solution [9], pyridinium bromochromate[10], hexamethylenetetramine-bromine [11], quinolinium fluorochromate [12], benzyltrimethyl ammonium dichloroiodate [13], benzyltrimethyl ammonium tribromide [14], and trialkylammonium fluorochromates [15]. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic studies of Cr(VI) species. Literature survey reveals that no report is available on the kinetics of the oxidation of

organic diols by B IDC. It was considered important to investigate the oxidation by B IDC. Hence, we report herein the kinetics of the oxidation of some organic diols by B IDC in different organic solvents.

Chromium(VI) reagents have long been used as powerful oxidants in organic chemistry; classical mechanistic studies established several general pathways for Cr(VI)-mediated oxidations including hydrogen-atom/ hydride abstraction steps and formation of substrate-Cr(VI) complexes that proceed to lower-valent chromium species (Cr(V), Cr(IV), Cr(III)) during the reaction sequence.

Interest in quaternary/heterocyclic ammonium and imidazolium-derived chromium(VI) salts (e.g., quinolinium, pyridinium, benzimidazolium dichromates) has grown because these reagents often combine ease of handling and tunable solubility with high oxidizing power. Benzimidazolium dichromate (B IDC) was introduced as a relatively stable Cr(VI) derivative whose physical stability and reactivity profile make it attractive for oxidation studies in non-aqueous media.

Several kinetic studies have characterized B IDC's reactivity in non-aqueous solvents (especially DMSO). Investigations on the oxidation of aliphatic alcohols and other substrates by B IDC in DMSO report clear kinetic patterns: in many cases the reaction shows first-order dependence on [B IDC] and either first-order or more complex dependence on substrate concentration .

Methodology

B IDC was prepared by the reported method [16] and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. The diols (BDH or Fluka) were distilled under reduced pressure before use. [1,1,2,2-²H₄] Ethanediol (DED) was prepared by reducing diethyl oxalate with lithium aluminium deuteride[17]. Its isotopic purity, determined by its NMR spectrum, was 91±3%. Toluene *p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen- ions. The solution of TsOH was standardized by titrating them against standard alkali. Using the described techniques, the organic solvents were made pure [18].

Analysis

Product analysis

Under kinetic condition *i.e.*, excess of diol over oxidant, product analysis was carried out. In this experiment, the propane 1-2 diol (0.1 mol) and B IDC (0.01 mol) were taken in 100 mL DMSO and it was then left in dark for a day to ensure completion of the reaction. The residue was treated an excess (200 mL) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept in a chiller for whole night. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed. The formation of DNP earlier and after recrystallization was 8.32 g (93%) and 7.24 g (81%) correspondingly. The DNP derivatives were found to be homogeneous by TLC. The identity of the products was established by comparing the m.p. of the DNP derivatives with the literature values [19]. In the oxidation of ethanediol and butane-1,3-diol, the identity of the products were confirmed by determining the m.p. with authentic samples of DNP of hydroxyethanal and 3-hydroxybutanal, respectively.

Stoichiometry

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by carrying out several sets of experiments with varying amounts of B IDC largely in excess over ethane diol. The estimation of unreacted B IDC showed the following reaction:

Kinetic measurements

The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions keeping a large excess (x10 or more) of diols over B IDC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (±0.1 K), by monitoring the decrease in [B IDC] spectrophotometrically at 364 nm for up to 80% of reaction by using spectrophotometer (Systronics, model no. 177). A graph between log [B IDC] and time was linear with $r^2 > 0.99$ and rate constant (k_{obs}) was obtained from it and for more than two runs reproducibility ±3% was observed. In correlation analyses coefficient of determination (R^2 or r^2), standard deviation (sd) and Exner's parameter (ψ) [20] was used.

Result and Discussion

The rate laws and other experimental data were attained for all the diols investigated. As the results were similar, only representative data are given here. The oxidation of diols by B IDC results in the formation of corresponding hydroxy carbonyl as the key product.

Rate laws. The reactions are first order with respect to B IDC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) do not depend on the initial concentration

of BIDC (Table 1). Fractional order dependency ($0 < \text{order} < 1$) was observed with respect to diols. A plot of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $1/[\text{Diol}]$ was straight line with positive intercept (**Figure 1**). This suggests the existence of following overall rate law and mechanism:

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K^\# [\text{Diol}] [\text{BIDC}]_t / (1 + K^\# [\text{Diol}]) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or, } 1/(\text{Rate}/[\text{BIDC}]_t) = 1/k_{obs} = 1/k_2 K^\# [\text{Diol}] + 1/k_2 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Here, } [\text{BIDC}]_t = [\text{BIDC}] + [\text{Complex}]$$

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of diols by BIDC at 308K, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Diol (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3[\text{BIDC}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3 k_{obs} (\text{s}^{-1})$			
		Ethanediol	Propane-1,2 diol	Butane-2,3 diol	Butane-1,2 diol
0.01	1.0	0.294	2.45	21.6	3.85
0.02	1.0	0.565	4.78	41.4	7.39
0.04	1.0	1.046	8.89	76.7	13.7
0.08	1.0	1.825	15.5	133	23.9
0.1	1.0	2.14	18.3	156	28.1
0.2	1.0	3.29	28.1	239	43.2
0.5	1.0	4.86	41.6	351	63.8
1.0	1.0	5.78	49.5	416	75.9
0.5	0.2	4.75	42.3	345	64.2
0.5	0.4	5.02	40.6	359	62.8
0.5	1.5	4.95	39.5	372	60.5
0.5	2.0	4.64	42.5	336	65.1
0.5	5.0	4.82	41.2	352	63.5
1.0	1.0	5.64*	50.6*	421*	72.6

Figure 1. A plot of $10^3 k_{obs}$ versus $[\text{Diol}]$ at 308 K

$$[\text{TsOH}] = 0.4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}; [\text{BIDC}] = 0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

Effect of temperature. The reactions were studied in the temperature range 298K to 328K for diols, using eq. (5) the value of $K^\#$ and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. For complex formation, the thermodynamic parameters (Table 2) and the activation parameters (Table 3) for decomposition of complexes were determined at different temperatures, from the value of $K^\#$ and k_2 respectively.

Table 2. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of Diols-BIDC complexes

Diol	$K^{\#}$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				ΔH_f kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS_f J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	$\Delta G_f(298K)$ kJ mol ⁻¹
	298K	308K	318K	328K			
Ethanediol	4.82	4.31	3.64	2.93	-15.9±1.1	-32±3.4	-6.4±0.8
Propane-1,2-diol	5.32	4.25	3.72	2.82	-19.1±0.6	-42±3.5	-6.6±0.9
Butane-2,3-diol	5.16	4.43	3.54	2.95	-17.9±0.1	-38±2.1	-6.6±0.5
Butane-1,2-diol	4.86	4.29	3.65	2.78	-17.3±1.5	-37±4.7	-6.5±1.1
Propane-1,3-diol	4.69	3.98	3.36	2.96	-15.1±0.2	-30±0.7	-6.3±0.2
Butane-1,3-diol	4.71	4.26	3.45	2.62	-18.4±1.7	-41±5.5	-6.4±1.3
Butane-1,4-diol	5.08	4.19	3.38	2.73	-19.3±0.4	-43±1.3	-6.5±0.3
Pentane-1,5-diol	4.65	3.86	3.42	2.58	-17.7±1.3	-39±4.2	-6.3±0.9
3-Methoxy-Butan-1-ol	5.23	3.92	3.56	2.64	-19.7±1.5	-45±4.9	-6.6±1.2
DED	4.95	4.18	3.26	2.89	-17.6±0.8	-38±2.6	-6.4±0.6

Table 3. Decomposition constants and activation parameters of Diols-BIDC complexes

Diol	$10^3 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^*(298K)$ mol ⁻¹)
	298K	308K	318K	328K			
Ethane diol	3.24	7.12	16.2	29.6	58.1±1.2	-98±3.9	87.2±0.9
Propane-1,2-diol	30.2	61.2	128	221	52.1±0.9	-100±3.4	81.6±0.8
Butane-2,3-diol	282	509	989	1582	44.9±1.1	-105±3.5	76.1±0.8
Butane-1,2-diol	47.8	93.6	198	332	50.8±1.3	-100±4.2	80.5±1.4
Propane-1,3-diol	7.32	18.2	39.1	93.7	65.8±1.1	-66±3.5	85.2±0.8
Butane-1,3-diol	9.45	23.9	55.2	123	66.9±0.1	-60±0.4	84.5±0.1
Butane-1,4-diol	11.8	27.2	65.7	149	66.4±0.9	-60±2.8	84.1±0.7
Pentane-1,5-diol	13.2	32.5	81.3	186	69.7±0.5	-49±1.6	83.8±0.4
3-Methoxy-Butan-1-ol	21.6	47.3	116	252	64.6±1.2	-61±3.9	82.6±0.9
DED	0.55	1.28	3.09	5.94	62.1±1.2	-99±3.7	91.5±0.8
k_H/k_D	5.91	5.56	5.24	4.98			

Effect of hydrogen ion.

In our present study TsOH is used as a source of [H⁺], with an increase in [H⁺] concentration, the rate constant increases. In a plot between log k_{obs} and log[H⁺], a straight line was seen (Figure 2). For all selected diols, the slope of the straight line is less than one, indicating that the order of reaction in relation to [H⁺] is less than one. Consequently, when acidity increases, correspondingly increases the rate of oxidation (Table 4). The relationship between rate constant and [H⁺] is as follows:

$$1/k_{obs} = a + b / [H^+]$$

Table 4. Effect of hydrogen ions on the oxidation of diols by BIDC

[Diol] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [BIDC] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, T = 308 K

[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)			
	Ethenediol	Propane-1,2 diol	Butane-2,3 diol	Butane-1,2 diol
0.05	1.99	12.7	74.6	16.9
0.1	2.63	20.4	136	28.8
0.2	3.91	33.1	243	46.6
0.4	5.78	49.5	415	75.9
0.8	8.29	77.6	742	129
1.0	9.35	89.2	897	151

Figure 2. A plot (3 + log k_{obs}) versus (2 + log[H⁺]) at 308 K

[Diol]= 1.0 mol dm⁻³; [BIDC] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile. The oxidation of diols by BIDC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the oxidation rate (Table 1).

Deuterium isotope effect. The oxidation of [1,1,2,2-²H₄] ethenediol (DED) was studied with BIDC to establish the significance of α-C-H bond fission in the rate-controlling step, by keeping all other parameters constant. Using deuterated ethenediol (DED) rate constant k₂ was measured. The outcomes (Table 2) showed that the formation constants of the complex of ethenediol and deuterated ethenediol are nearly close but rates of their decomposition (Table 3) indicated a deuterium isotope effect (k_H/k_D = 5.78 at 308K). In present study, the value of kinetic isotope effect decreases with increase in temperature.

Effect of solvent

Swain et al. [21] believed that the specific solvation is determined principally by the acidity and the basicity of the solvent. The data are analysed using a two-parameter equation involving anion-solvating tendency (A) and cation-solvating tendency (B):

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \tag{6}$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. (A+B) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of Eq. (6), separately with A and B and with (A + B):

$$\log k_2 = 0.21 \pm 0.01 A + 1.59 \pm 0.008 B - 3.01 \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9995, sd = 0.0095, n = 19, \psi = 0.02, T = 308 \pm 1 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = -0.016 \pm 0.52 A - 1.91 \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.015, sd = 0.423, n = 19, \psi = 1.01, T = 308 \pm 1 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.57 \pm 0.04 B - 2.94 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9902, sd = 0.042, n = 19, \psi = 0.11, T = 308 \pm 1 \text{ K}$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.13 \pm 0.17 (A + B) - 2.96 \quad (10)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7076, sd = 0.2288, n = 19, \psi = 0.56, T = 308 \pm 1 \text{ K}$$

The rates of oxidation of propane-1,2 diol in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation solvation alone accounts for ca. 99% of the data. The correlation with anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by (A+B), also accounted for ca. 70% of the data.

Table 5. Solvent effect on the oxidation of propane-1,2 diol by B IDC at 308K

Solvent	$10^3 k_2$ (sec ⁻¹)	Solvent	$10^3 k_2$ (sec ⁻¹)
DMSO	61.2	Benzene	9.1
DMF	34.8	Dioxan	12.4
Acetophenone	29.6	Cyclohexane	1.3
Nitrobenzene	26.5	tert-Butyl alcohol	7.4
Acetone	21.8	Carbon disulfide	4.0
Tetrahydrofurane	12.2	1,2-Dichloroethane	22.9
Acetic acid	2.5	Dichloromethane	21.7
Ethyl Acetate	9.5	Butanone	16.7
Chloroform	17.1	1,2-Dimethoxy ethane	6.8
Toluene	7.3		

Discussion

The activation entropies and enthalpies of the oxidation of vicinal diols showed poor correlation ($r^2 = 0.9041$). The correlation was checked with Exner's criterion [22]. The Exner plot between the values of $\log k_2$ at 298K and 328K, for vicinal diols was linear (**Figure 3**) with perfect correlation (slope 0.8912, $r^2 = 0.9997$). The value of isokinetic temperature is 1724 ± 39 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the substrates are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of the activation.

Mechanism. The absence of any effect of a radical scavenger, acrylonitrile on the reaction rate, it is unlikely that oxidation through one electron is operative. From the product analysis, DNP was confirmed. Hence, it shows that under the experimental conditions employed in the present work, diols were oxidized to the corresponding hydroxy carbonyls. The presence of deuterium isotope effect confirms the cleavage of an α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The acid-catalysis is examined as earlier protonation of BDC to produce BIDCH⁺.

A mechanism depicted in scheme 1 account for the experimental results. The rate law based on the mechanism proposed in **scheme 1**, can be obtained as below:

Applying the equilibrium treatment, BDC can be determined:

$$-d[\text{BDC}]/dt = k_2 [\text{R}] = k_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{Diol}] [\text{BDC}] [\text{H}^+] \quad (13)$$

$$-d[\text{BDC}]/dt = \frac{k_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{Diol}] [\text{BDC}]_t [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{Diol}] [\text{H}^+]} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{-d[\text{BDC}]/dt}{[\text{BDC}]_t} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{Diol}] [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{Diol}] [\text{H}^+]} \quad (15)$$

Here, $[\text{BDC}]_t = [\text{BDC}] + [\text{Complex}]$, where K_1 is small and [B] formed will undergo reaction with diol.

$$\text{or, } 1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{Diol}] [\text{H}^+] + 1/k_2 \quad (16)$$

Comparing equation (5) with (16), we get

$$K = K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+] \quad (17)$$

The hydride-ion transfer may occur either by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process or by cyclic process *via* chromate ester. Kwart and Nickle [25] have shown that a dependence of k_H/k_D on temperature, the loss of hydrogen proceeds through a concerted cyclic process. The data for protio- and deuterio-ethandiol, fitted to the familiar expression-

$$k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(-\Delta E_a/RT) \quad (18)$$

The activation energy difference for k_H/k_D is *ca* 4.66 kJ mol⁻¹ which decided by final results agrees that the activation entropy (ΔS^*) and zero-point energy difference for both C-D and C-H bonds (*ca*. 4.5 kJ mol⁻¹) are nearly equal in the present reaction.

BI = benzimidazolium

Scheme 1. Mechanism for the oxidation of ethanediol by BDC

It is agreeing with symmetrical transition state properties.[26,27]. Bordwell [28] has documented very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step bimolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and in present study it is evident that the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic bimolecular process. The only truly symmetrical process involving linear transfer of hydrogen is intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions characterized by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic

transition state [29]. Littler [30] has also shown that cyclic hydride transfer, in alcohol oxidation by Cr(VI), involves six electrons which resembles with Huckel-type system, is an allowed process. The negative entropy of activation in conjunction with other experimental data supports the suggested mechanism.

Initially Cr(VI) is reduced to Cr(IV). It is likely to react with another Cr(VI) to generate Cr(V) which is then reduced in a fast step to the ultimate product Cr(III). Such a sequence of reactions in Cr(VI) oxidations is well known. [16]

Conclusion

The kinetics of oxidation of diols with BDC in DMSO medium has been studied. There is no possibility of one electron mechanism since, there is no polymerization of acrylonitrile. The oxidation product of the reaction was corresponding hydroxy carbonyl. The reaction exhibited first-order kinetics with respect to oxidant. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics observed with substrate. The reaction is catalysed by TsOH and protonated BDC is suggested to be the reactive oxidising species. An α -C-H bond fission showed in slow step. A mechanism involving in the rate-determining oxidative breakdown of complex through hydride-ion transfer from diol to BDC to give final product is proposed.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the Department of Chemistry, MLS University, Udaipur (India) for providing the research facilities developed under RUSA 2.0 (No. F30 (16) SPD/RUSA/2016/178 dated 31 March 2020)

References

1. S. Priyadarshinia, P.S. Gurua, R. DS, S. Dash, *Cr(VI) oxidation of cholesterol-A kinetic study using n-Cetylpicolinium dichromates, A class of novel phase transfer oxidants. Kinetics and Catalysis*, **60**, 147–154 (2019).
doi: 10.1134/S0023158419020083
2. V.S. Malik, B.H. Asghar, S.S Mansoor, *Kinetics and the mechanism of oxidation of methoxy benzaldehydes by benzimidazolium fluorochromate in an aqueous acetic acid medium. J Taibah Univ Sci.* **10**, 131-138 (2016).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtusci.2015.05.009>
3. A. Singadiya, R. Jangir, P. Bishnoi and Om Prakash , *oxidation kinetics and influence of media on some α -hydroxy acids by 2-picolinium chlorochromate; Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, **15(4)**, 2512 (2022).
<http://doi.org/10.31788/RJC.2022.1547088>
4. B. Amb, B.L. Hiran, *Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzaldehyde and 4-nitrobenzaldehyde by Pyridinium Dichromate in Aqueous Acetic acid medium. Oxid Commun.* **35**, 560-568 (2012).
<https://scibulcom.net/en/article/8RjnUTmOPAhOHOTrrkJg>
5. D. Panday and S. Kothari, *Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of diols by butyltriphenylphosphonium dichromate, Indian Journal of Chemistry*, **50B**, 918-925 (2011).
6. R. Kalal, and D. Panday, *Kinetics and mechanistic study of the oxidation of some diols by isoquinolinium dichromate in aqueous acetic acid medium, Oxidation Communications.*, **44**, 513-522 (2021).
7. S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Correlation analysis of reactivity in the oxidation of some organic diols by tripropylammonium fluorochromate in non-aqueous media , Arabian Journal of Chemistry* **9**, S602–S60 (2016). Doi: 10.1016/j.arabjc.2011.07.004
8. K. Loonker, P. K. Sharma and Kalyan K. Banerji, *Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Diols by 2,2'-Bipyridinium Chlorochromate, J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1997, 242-243.
Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1039/A606277F>
9. Sharma, V., Sharma, P.K. and Banerji, K.K. *Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of diols by bromine in acid solution. Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)* **110**, 65-73 (1998). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02871910>
10. D. Mathur, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of diols by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide, Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, **107**, 133-141 (1995).
11. H. Gangwani, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Kinetics and Mechanism of oxidation of diols by Hexamethylenetetramine-bromine, Journal of Chemical Research*, **23**, 180-181(1999). DOI:10.1177/174751989902300305
12. K. Choudhary, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of diols by quinolinium fluorochromate, Indian Journal of Chemistry*, **38A**, 325 – 330 (1999).
13. Mehla, S.K., Kothari, S., Banerji, K.K., *Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some diols by benzyltrimethylammonium dichloriodate, Oxid. Commun.* **23**, 229-237 (2000).
14. G. Goswami, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some diols by benzyltrimethylammonium tribromide, Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, **113**, 43–54 (2001).

17. S. Ghammamy, S. Khorsandtabar, A. Moghimi, and H. Sahebalzamani, Oxidation of some organic diols with trialkylammonium fluorochromates(VI), $R_3NH[CrO_3F]$, ($R= CH_3, C_2H_5, C_3H_7$ and C_4H_9) at room temperature and under microwave condition, *J. Mex. Chem. Soc.*, 53, 41-43 (2009).
18. Q.H. Meng, J.C. Feng, N.S. Bian, B. Leu, and C.C. Li, Benzimidazolium dichromate a new reagent for selective oxidation under microwave irradiation, *Synth. Commun.*, 28,1097 (1998). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00397919808003079>
19. T. J. Kemp and W. A. Waters: The mechanisms of oxidation of formaldehyde and formic acid by ions of Chromium (VI), Vanadium (V) and Cobalt (III). *Proc. Roy. Soc. Ser A*, 274, 480-499 (1963).
20. Doi: 10.1098/rspa.1963.0145
21. J. A. Riddick and W. B. Bunger, In *Techniques of Chemistry*, Vol. 2, Wiley-Interscience, New York (1970).
22. S. Coffey (ed.), *Rodd's Chemistry of Carbon Compounds*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2nd Ed., 1965, Vol. I D; E. H. Rodd (ed.), *Chemistry of Carbon Compounds*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1951, Vol. I A; J. Buckingham et al (ed.), *Dictionary of Organic Compounds*, Chapman and Hall, New York, V Ed., 1982, Vol., 3; R. C. West, *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics*, CRC Press, Ohio, 58th Ed., 1977-78, Vol. 3.
23. O. EXNER: Additive Physical Properties. I. General Relationships and Problems of Statistical Nature. *Collect Czech Chem Commun*, 31, 3222 (1966).
24. C.G. Swain, M.S. Swain, A.L. Powell, S. Alumni, Solvent effects on chemical reactivity. evaluation of anion and cation solvation components, *J Am Chem Soc.* 105, 502-513(1983).
25. O. EXNERS: The Enthalpy and Entropy Relationship. *Prog Phys Org Chem*, 10, 411 (1973).
26. R. Kalal and D. Panday, Kinetics and correlation analysis of reactivity in the oxidation of aliphatic primary alcohols by isoquinolinium dichromate in non-aqueous medium, *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*. 98, 100009 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jics.2021.100009>
27. K. B. Wiberg: *Physical Organic Chemistry*. John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1964, p. 416.
28. H. Kwart and J.H. Nickle: Transition States in Chromium (VI) Oxidation of Alcohols. *J Am Chem Soc*, 95, 3394-96 (1973). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00791a059>
29. H. Kwart and H. C. Latimer: Kinetics deuterium isotope criterion for concertedness. *J Am Chem Soc*, 93, 3770-71 (1971). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja00744a038>
30. H. Kwart and J. Slutsky: Transition-state structure in thermal β -cis-elimination of esters. *J Chem Soc Chem Commun*, 21, 1182-83 (1972). <https://doi.org/10.1039/C39720001182>.
31. F. G. Bordwell: How Common Are Base-Initiated, Concerted 1,2 Eliminations? *Acc Chem Res*, 5, 374-81 (1972). <https://doi.org/10.1021/ar50059a003>
32. R. B. Woodward and R. Hoffmann: The Conservation of orbital symmetry. *Agnew Chem Int Ed Engl*, 8, 781-853 (1969). 3. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.196907811>.
33. J. S. Littler: Oxidation of Olefins, Alcohols, Glycols and other Organic Compounds, by Inorganic Oxidants such as Chromium(VI), Manganese(VII), Iodine(VII), Lead(IV), Vanadium(V) and Halogens, Considered in the light of the selection rules for electrocyclic reactions. *Tetrahedron*, 27, 81-91 (1971). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020\(01\)92399-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4020(01)92399-3)
34. G. Milazzo, S. Caroli, V. K. Sharma: *Tables of standard electrode metal potentials*. Wiley & Sons, New York, 1978.
35. <https://www.ias.ac.in/article/fulltext/jcsc/107/02/0133-0141>